

Search strings used for the literature review on modeling methods for DBI (search conducted in September 2022)

Web of Science			AIS eLibrary		Scopus
Search in titles	Search in abstracts	Search in keywords	Search in abstracts	Search in titles	Search in titles / abstract / keywords (limited to LNBIP / LNISO as these are not indexed in Web of Science)
<p>104 results: AB=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business) AND AB=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain))</p>	<p>8 results: TI=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business) AND TI=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain))</p>	<p>29 results: AK=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business) AND AK=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain))</p>	<p>61 results: abstract:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling) AND abstract:(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>1 result: title:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling) AND title:(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>36 results: TITLE-ABS-KEY (digital AND transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise AND transformation OR business AND transformation OR organi*ational AND transformation OR business AND innovation OR business AND model AND innovation OR digital AND innovation OR organi*ational AND change OR digital AND business) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((enterprise OR conceptual OR domain) PRE/0 model*ing)</p>

Web of Science			AIS eLibrary		Scopus
<p>176 results: AB=(strateg*) AND AB=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) NOT AB=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>18 results: TI=(strateg*) AND TI=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) NOT TI=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>36 results: AK=(strateg*) AND AK=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) NOT AK=(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>237 results: abstract:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling) AND abstract:strateg* NOT abstract:(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>8 results: title:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling) AND title:strateg* NOT title:(digital transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise transformation OR business transformation OR organi?ational transformation OR business innovation OR business model innovation OR digital innovation OR organi?ational change OR digital business)</p>	<p>58 results: TITLE-ABS-KEY (strateg*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((enterprise OR conceptual OR domain) PRE/0 model*ing) AND NOT TITLE-ABS-KEY (digital AND transformation OR digitalization OR enterprise AND transformation OR business AND transformation OR organi?ational AND transformation OR business AND innovation OR business AND model AND innovation OR digital AND innovation OR organi?ational AND change OR digital AND business) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Lecture Notes In Business Information Processing") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Lecture Notes In Information Systems And Organisation"))</p>

Web of Science			AIS eLibrary		Scopus
<p>278 results: AB=(participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light\$weight OR grass\$root*) AND AB=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) and Computer Science Information Systems or Computer Science Theory Methods or Computer Science Software Engineering or Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications or Operations Research Management Science or Management or Information Science Library Science or Business or Social Sciences Interdisciplinary or Economics or Psychology Multidisciplinary or Ergonomics or Business Finance (Web of Science Categories)</p>	<p>39 results: TI=(participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light\$weight OR grass\$root*) AND TI=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) and Computer Science Information Systems or Computer Science Theory Methods or Computer Science Software Engineering or Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications or Operations Research Management Science or Management or Information Science Library Science or Business or Social Sciences Interdisciplinary or Economics or Psychology Multidisciplinary or Ergonomics or Business Finance (Web of Science Categories) and Lightweight Em Etc. (Exclude – Filter by Marked List)</p>	<p>78 results: AK=(participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light\$weight OR grass\$root*) AND AK=(model\$ing NEAR/0 (enterprise OR conceptual OR domain)) and Computer Science Information Systems or Operations Research Management Science or Computer Science Theory Methods or Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications or Information Science Library Science or Management (Web of Science Categories)</p>	<p>262 results: abstract:(participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light\$weight OR grass\$root\$) AND abstract:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling)</p>	<p>3 results: title:(participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light\$weight OR grass\$root\$) AND title:(enterprise modeling OR domain modeling OR conceptual modeling)</p>	<p>73 results: TITLE-ABS-KEY (participat* OR collaborative OR interactive OR natural OR light*\$weight OR grass*\$root*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((enterprise OR conceptual OR domain) PRE/0 model*\$ing) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Lecture Notes In Business Information Processing") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Lecture Notes In Information Systems And Organisation"))</p>